

Atomic and electronic properties of 2D Chevrel phases: A case study of the superatomic two-dimensional semiconductor $\text{Re}_6\text{Se}_8\text{Cl}_2$

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Abstract

The design of two-dimensional superatomic materials, which form their atomic structures through covalently bonded clusters with variable chemical compositions, will enable the development of new materials with promised electronic properties that are beneficial for modern nanoelectronics. This paper presents *ab initio* calculations of the atomic and electronic structures of both bulk and 2D $\text{Re}_6\text{Se}_8\text{Cl}_2$. The calculations were carried out using density functional theory, incorporating noncollinear spin density and the pseudopotential method. The results include data on the atomic structure, band gap value, formation energy of the $\text{Re}_6\text{Se}_8\text{Cl}_2$ 2D layer, and the redistribution of atomic charges within the structures. The differences in effective masses for electrons and holes in the two-dimensional and bulk $\text{Re}_6\text{Se}_8\text{Cl}_2$ materials are demonstrated, along with an explanation of how these differences impact their transport properties. The findings are expected to be of great significance for the design, synthesis, and implementation of new two-dimensional superatomic materials with controlled properties in modern nanoelectronics.

Keywords

superatomic 2D materials, atomic and electronic structure, *ab initio* calculations, band gap, atomic charges, effective masses

1. Introduction

The superatomic compound $\text{Re}_6\text{Se}_8\text{Cl}_2$ is a two-dimensional structural analog of the Chevrel phase materials $M_x\text{Mo}_6E_8$ (where M = metal, E = S, Se, Te) [1–5]. These materials are referred to as "superatomic crystals" because they are composed of molecular clusters, and some of them are characterized by a layered structure in which $[\text{Re}_6\text{Se}_8]$ clusters are covalently bonded into layers

capped by terminal chlorine atoms [6–8]. In [8], it was demonstrated that strong in-plane intercluster bonding and weak interlayer interactions allow for mechanical exfoliation of $\text{Re}_6\text{Se}_8\text{Cl}_2$ layers. The authors of [8] also showed that bulk $\text{Re}_6\text{Se}_8\text{Cl}_2$ is an indirect bandgap semiconductor with an electronic bandgap of 1.58 ± 0.03 eV, an optical bandgap of 1.48 ± 0.01 eV, and a large exciton binding energy of around 100 meV. Strong coupling of electrons with intercluster optical phonons [9, 10] leads

to the emergence of superconductivity in this material. It was shown that polaron formation protects excitons from scattering by lattice phonons, resulting in quasi-ballistic electron energy transport over several micrometers [10]. Furthermore, an exceptionally long exciton free path of approximately 1 mm was discovered, which opens up the possibility of creating ballistic exciton transistors. In a recent study by Shih et al. [11], it was found that the narrow exciton bandwidth, which can be explained by temperature-dependent renormalization due to optical phonons, plays a crucial role in the stability of acoustic polarons in $\text{Re}_6\text{Se}_8\text{Cl}_2$. Within this mechanism, the polaron binding energy decreases with decreasing temperature.

Transition this material into a two-dimensional state and altering its chemical composition may yield even more intriguing properties, with the potential to design and develop advanced and promising nanoelectronic materials based on it. Therefore, the aim of our research was to theoretically investigate and detail understand the differences in atomic and electronic properties between the bulk and two-dimensional states of $\text{Re}_6\text{Se}_8\text{Cl}_2$.

2. Calculation methods

The calculations of atomic structures and electronic properties were carried out using the VASP package [12–14]. The generalized gradient approximation in the form of GGA–PBE [15] was employed in the PAW pseudopotentials [16, 17]. Spin-orbit coupling and spin polarization were taken into account in the calculations [18]. Van der Waals interactions were included using the Grimme DFT-D3 semi-empirical method [19] to account for inter-layer interactions. For testing the properties of the bulk unit cell of $\text{Re}_6\text{Se}_8\text{Cl}_2$, a k -point mesh of $9 \times 9 \times 7$ was used. For the monolayer, a k -point mesh of $9 \times 9 \times 1$ was applied using the Monkhorst–Pack scheme [20]. The optimization of the atomic structure was continued until the forces converged to a precision of 10^{-4} eV/nm.

3. Results and discussion

The bulk structure of $\text{Re}_6\text{Se}_8\text{Cl}_2$ is characterized by a triclinic space group P-1, with experimental lattice parameters of $a = 0.65784(7)$ nm, $b = 0.66194(8)$ nm, $c = 0.88010(9)$ nm, and angles $\alpha = 76.708(9)^\circ$, $\beta = 70.204(9)^\circ$, and $\gamma = 86.368(9)^\circ$ (Fig. 1). The volume of the unit cell is $V = 0.35088(6)$ nm³ [8]. In our study, a full structural relaxation of the unit cell was performed, maintaining its symmetry while allowing the atomic coordinates to change. As a result, our theoretical calculations yield the following values for the lattice parameters: $a = 0.65599$ nm, $b = 0.66031$ nm, and $c = 0.87116$ nm, with angles $\alpha = 76.478^\circ$, $\beta = 69.883^\circ$, and $\gamma = 86.532^\circ$, and a unit cell volume of $V = 0.34442$ nm³. Figure 1 shows the bulk unit cell with the specified atomic positions and lattice parameters. The interlayer distance in the $\text{Re}_6\text{Se}_8\text{Cl}_2$

Figure 1. The bulk structure of $\text{Re}_6\text{Se}_8\text{Cl}_2$

unit cell is $d = 0.25930$ nm. It is evident that our theoretical data agree well with the experimental data, with errors in the lattice constants of only $\epsilon_a = 0.28\%$, $\epsilon_b = 0.25\%$, and $\epsilon_c = 1.02\%$. For the angles, the errors are $\epsilon_\alpha = 0.30\%$, $\epsilon_\beta = 0.46\%$, and $\epsilon_\gamma = 0.19\%$, respectively.

To build the most stable 2D layer from the bulk structure of $\text{Re}_6\text{Se}_8\text{Cl}_2$, we used the methodology proposed by Vahdat [21]. This methodology is based on a machine learning approach and allows to determine of the most favorable two-dimensional structure from the three-dimensional bulk material. The resulting 2D layer for $\text{Re}_6\text{Se}_8\text{Cl}_2$ is shown in Fig. 2. Next, the atomic relaxation of the layer was performed, also preserving symmetry and allowing for atomic displacements. For this 2D layer, the equilibrium lattice parameters were determined to be $a = 0.65807$ nm and $b = 0.66075$ nm, with angles $\alpha = 89.6500^\circ$, $\beta = 89.7870^\circ$, and $\gamma = 86.0720^\circ$. It is observed that during the relaxation of the 2D layer,

Figure 2. The 2D layer of $\text{Re}_6\text{Se}_8\text{Cl}_2$

to relieve surface stresses, the lattice parameter a changes more significantly compared to parameter b , resulting in an increase in the cross-sectional area in the XY plane. To eliminate interactions between $\text{Re}_6\text{Se}_8\text{Cl}_2$ layers during their translation along the Z -axis, we set the lattice parameter c to 2.86201 nm. According to our calculations, the formation of a 2D layer from bulk $\text{Re}_6\text{Se}_8\text{Cl}_2$ by mechanical exfoliation requires an energy expenditure of approximately 0.65 eV per formula unit. This energy value was determined using the following expression:

$$E_{\text{form}} = E_{2\text{D}} - E_{\text{bulk}},$$

where $E_{2\text{D}}$ is the total energy of the 2D layer of $\text{Re}_6\text{Se}_8\text{Cl}_2$ and E_{bulk} is the total energy of the bulk material [22]. Thus, it is evident that the obtained value for the energy required to form a two-dimensional layer of $\text{Re}_6\text{Se}_8\text{Cl}_2$ is significantly higher than that for the monolayer ReSeCl , which is 0.22 eV/fu [23], and the monolayer ReSe_2 , which is 0.23 eV/fu [24].

The electronic structure analysis reveals that for the bulk material the bandgap is 1.11 eV and the $\text{Re}_6\text{Se}_8\text{Cl}_2$ is an indirect bandgap semiconductor. The "top" of the valence band is localized at the k -point Γ (0, 0, 0), while the "bottom" of the conduction band is located at the k -point T (0, 0.444, 0.5) in the Brillouin zone. For the 2D structure of $\text{Re}_6\text{Se}_8\text{Cl}_2$, the bandgap increases to 1.34 eV. Thus, the bandgap of the 2D layer is larger compared to the bulk material. The 2D structure remains an indirect bandgap semiconductor, but the localization of the "top" of the valence band and the "bottom" of the conduction band changes. Specifically, the "top" of the valence band is now located at the k -point (0.111, -0.111, 0), while the "bottom" of the conduction band is at the k -point (0, -0.444, 0). The obtained bandgap values for both the bulk and 2D $\text{Re}_6\text{Se}_8\text{Cl}_2$ are consistent with other reported data [25]. For an accurate assessment of the bandgap,

Table 1. Charges on atoms according to the Bader method in units of electrons (average charge values are provided)

Structure	Re	Se	Cl
2D	-0.596	+0.325	-0.489
bulk	-0.595	+0.318	-0.512

Table 2. Effective masses for electrons (m_e) and holes (m_h) in the bulk and 2D materials

Direction	m_e^*	m_h^*
bulk $\text{Re}_6\text{Se}_8\text{Cl}_2$		
k -path $G \rightarrow X$	$1.571m_0$	$0.701m_0$
k -path $G \rightarrow Y$	$9.545m_0$	$1.105m_0$
2D layer $\text{Re}_6\text{Se}_8\text{Cl}_2$		
k -path $G \rightarrow X$	$1.294m_0$	$1.643m_0$
k -path $G \rightarrow Y$	$5.644m_0$	$2.216m_0$

we employed the local potential approximation (LMBJ-potential) [26, 27], which is optimal for two-dimensional materials.

Next, the analysis of the charge distribution for the $\text{Re}_6\text{Se}_8\text{Cl}_2$ structures was conducted. The charge on the atoms was calculated using the Bader method [28]. It is observed that the charges on the rhenium atoms remain almost unchanged when transitioning from bulk to 2D state. This is likely due to the presence of unpaired electrons on Re atoms, which are shielded by Se atoms through the formation of stable Re–Se bonds [8, 29]. The charge on Se atoms increases by approximately $0.007e$, while the charge on Cl atoms decreases by $0.023e$ (Table 1). This charge transfer influences on the bandgap increase in the two-dimensional structure of $\text{Re}_6\text{Se}_8\text{Cl}_2$. According to Bader's analysis, during forming bulk and 2D materials of $\text{Re}_6\text{Se}_8\text{Cl}_2$ from the chemical elements Re, Se, and Cl, there is a charge transfer from Re atoms to Se and Cl atoms.

Next, to understand the processes of energy and information transfer in these materials, we calculated the effective mass for electrons and holes in the layer planes formed by the $\text{Re}_6\text{Se}_8\text{Cl}_2$ clusters, for both the bulk and 2D materials. We computed the effective masses along the high-symmetry directions $G \rightarrow X$ and $G \rightarrow Y$. For the bulk material, the calculated values are as follows: the effective mass of the electron is $1.571m_0$ and for the hole is $0.701m_0$ along the $G \rightarrow X$ direction, where m_0 is the free electron mass. Along the $G \rightarrow Y$ direction, the effective masses of the electron and hole are $9.545m_0$ and $1.105m_0$, respectively. However, for the 2D material, the effective masses for electrons and holes differ and are as follows: the effective mass of the electron is $1.294m_0$ and for the hole is $1.643m_0$ along the $G \rightarrow X$ direction, while along the $G \rightarrow Y$ direction, the effective masses of the electron and hole are $5.644m_0$ and $2.216m_0$, respectively. Thus, it is evident that the 2D material $\text{Re}_6\text{Se}_8\text{Cl}_2$ exhibits enhanced electron transport properties along the $G \rightarrow X$ direction compared to the bulk material. However, for holes, the transport properties are reduced in both the $G \rightarrow X$ and $G \rightarrow Y$ directions. These results are consistent with those in [10], where the authors first predicted enhanced transport properties for single crystals of $\text{Re}_6\text{Se}_8\text{Cl}_2$. We are the first to show that the 2D materials of $\text{Re}_6\text{Se}_8\text{Cl}_2$ have better electron transport properties compared to the bulk material. Table 2 presents the calculated values for the effective masses of electrons and holes for both the bulk and 2D $\text{Re}_6\text{Se}_8\text{Cl}_2$ materials.

4. Conclusion

In this work, quantum mechanical calculations of the atomic and electronic structure for both bulk and two-dimensional layers of $\text{Re}_6\text{Se}_8\text{Cl}_2$ have been performed. The calculations show that during the relaxation of the 2D layer, to relieve surface stresses, the lattice parameter a changes more significantly (increasing by 0.31%)

compared to parameter b , leading to an increase in the surface area of the layer. It is demonstrated the band-gap of the $\text{Re}_6\text{Se}_8\text{Cl}_2$ layer increases comparably to the bulk material, and the 2D structure remains an indirect band-gap semiconductor. Additionally, the charge transfer from Re atoms to Se and Cl atoms occurs during the formation of both the bulk and 2D $\text{Re}_6\text{Se}_8\text{Cl}_2$ materials from the chemical elements Re, Se, and Cl. Analysis of the effective masses for electrons and holes indicates that the 2D material $\text{Re}_6\text{Se}_8\text{Cl}_2$ exhibits enhanced electron transport properties along the $G \rightarrow X$ direction compared to the bulk material. However, for holes, the transport properties are reduced in both the $G \rightarrow X$ and $G \rightarrow Y$ directions.

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